
Role of NABARD in Agriculture Development

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Abstract:

NABARD is set up by the Government of India as a development bank with the mandate of facilitating credit flow for promotion and development of agriculture and integrated rural development. The mandate also covers supporting all other allied economic activities in rural areas, promoting sustainable rural development and ushering in prosperity in the rural areas. With a capital base of Rs 2,000 crore provided by the Government of India and Reserve Bank of India, it operates through its head office at Mumbai, 28 regional offices situated in state capitals and 391 district offices at districts. The objective of this research is To Study about of NABARD bank. And NABARD Role in Agricultural sector development. Research is based on secondary data. The various functions of NABARD are Credit Functions, Developmental and Promotional Functions, Supervisory Functions, Institutional and Capacity building, Role in Training etc. The paper attempts to analyze the role of NABARD and its functioning in development of rural India.

Introduction:

NABARD is an apex body in agricultural and rural development area they handle policy, planning and operational activities of that area. NABARD is set up by government of India for the purpose of facilitating credit flow for promotion, refinancing, development of agricultural and rural development purpose. NABARD bank head office at Mumbai. The Government of India and Reserve Bank of India invested (Capital) 2000 Crore in NABARD. The Government of India and Reserve Banks of India provide fund to NABARD. NABARD bank central office in Mumbai with 28 Regional offices in various states and 391 District level offices. The bank facilitated the co-operative banks, regional rural banks, Commercial banks to improving credit flow. The NABARD also refinance to farm sector, non-farm sector, women and weaker sector peoples etc. The RBI set up CRAFICARD (The Committee to Review Arrangements for Institutional Credit for Agriculture and Rural Development) on his report they

recommended in November 1979 to RBI establishing the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural development bank. That result the NABARD established in 12 July 1982.

Objective of the Study:

1. To Study Concept of NABARD bank.
2. To Study NABARD Role in Agricultural sector development.

Methodology:

The study is descriptive nature. The Study based on secondary data collected from various sources Magazines, Internet Website, News Paper, Research Papers and journals

About NABARD Bank:

Functions of NABARD:

1) Credit Functions: NABARD provide credit facilities to agricultural and rural development sector peoples, institutions, Banks, Industries etc.

2) Supervisory Function: NABARD bank play role of supervisory. The NABARD comes under Supervision of Reserve Bank of India the RBI directly control and guide to NABARD. The NABARD supervise for proper functioning of co-operative banks and Regional Rural banks.

3) Developmental and Promotional Functions: In Promotional and Development function is credit planning, Funds Provide for Special Projects, Water Shed Development Fund, Livelihood Development, Environmental Protection , Kisan Credit Card, Farmers Club Programme, Government Sponsored Scheme, etc. Scheme Introduced NABARD for the purpose of Development and Promotional.

4) Institutional and Capacity Building: The NABARD help to Co-operative banks and RRBs for prepare development action plans. Play role of intermediate of State Government and Co-operative banks. Provide guidance to other Co-operative banks for the purpose of MoUs. Provide financial assistance, technical knowledge, monitoring and evaluation cells to Co-operative banks and RRBs and also Provide Staff Training facilities.

5) Training and Development Function: The NABARD Provide training facilities to bank Staff. Provide training for senior and middle level employees of Co-operative, RRBs and Commercial banks. Also the NABARD provide financial assistance to banks for computerization of operation, human resource development and Management improvement activates. NABARD provide training facilities in National Bank Staff College, Lucknow, National Bank Training Centre, Lucknow, Zonal Training Centre, Hyderabad, Regional Training Centre, Mangalore, Regional Training Centre, Bolpur ,Bankers Institute of Rural Development , Lucknow

NABARD Role:

- It is an apex refinancing institution providing credit facilities to agricultural sector.
- NABARD is an apex body for making planning, operations and polices for the field of agricultural and rural development.
- It is apex agency for co-ordinate to Agricultural and Rural development activities and State Government, Central Government, RBI, National Level Institution for implementation of new Schemes.
- NABARD Prepare annual basis credit plans for all districts in the country and these plans for the base for annual credit plans of all rural financial agencies.
- The NABARD promotes Research in the field of agricultural and rural development.

Also NABARD help to generation of employment in rural areas. They introduced lot of refinance and promotional schemes for agricultural development purpose. The focus has been on greater credit flow and provision of linkages for small, cottage and village industries, handicrafts and other rural crafts and service sector in the decentralized sector in the rural areas.

Objectives of NABARD Bank:

- 1) Provide credit to agriculture and rural sector development
- 2) Supervise Agricultural and Rural financial Institutions
- 3) Promote practices, policies and innovation conducive to rural development

Mission of NABARD Bank:

Provide equal support to agricultural and rural prosperity through effective financial support, Services, Institutional development and other innovative strategy etc. and Provide refinance facility.

Associates of NABARD:

Total eight international associated of this Institutes. They are as follow.

- 1) World Bank Group & the International Development Association
- 2) KfW of Germany
- 3) Swiss Agency for Development & Cooperation
- 4) Commission on European Community
- 5) Asian Pacific Agricultural Credit Association
- 6) International Fund for Agricultural Development
- 7) GTZ of Germany
- 8) Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries.

These institutes are also providing finance, guidance for implementation schemes.

NABARD Role in Agricultural Development: as under

1. Credit Planning: Provide credit facilities to customer block-wise, bank-wise, farm wise and Nonfarm wise sector. ground level planning exercise facilitates each branch of the bank in the district to prepare a village level credit plan, develop strategy to implement the plan to achieve physical & financial targets, which are monitored by individual bank for all its branches and reviewed by the District Level Coordination Committee quarterly block-wise, bank-wise & activity-wise. NABARD target to institutional credit for agricultural sector to be raise from Ru.10 lakh crore in 2017-18 to raise Ru. 11 lakh crore in 2018-19. At national level NABARD facilitates GoI, RBI and State Governments to evolve policy that can accelerate credit flow for integrated rural development.

2. Seasonal Agricultural Finance: NABARD provide seasonal credit for agricultural and rural activities. Provide short-term credit to farmers to raise seasonal crops production. NABARD coordinated the interest subvention scheme in respect of cooperative banks and RRBs.

3. Refinance Facility to Agricultural Sector: The institute support to various agricultural and rural activates for the purpose of development of this sector.

4. Investment Credit Support: NABARD provide credit to investment purpose for asset creation, purchase new assets, Technology up gradation, equipment development etc. its resulting increased production.

5. Kisan Credit Card Scheme (KCC): NABARD introduced Kisan Credit Card with the help of this scheme loan facilities provide to farmers crop loans by providing adequate, timely, cost effective and seasonal agricultural loan provide to NABARD with single window system. Current NABARD extension of kisan Credit Card Scheme facilities to fisheries and animal husbandry farmers. Also this scheme provides short term loan and covered under Personal Accident Insurance Scheme against accidental death and permanent disability.

6. Watershed Development: NABARD has been work for watershed development as a comprehensive approach to enhance productivity of dry land through conserving soil, rainwater and vegetation. It is pioneering model in community based natural resource management Participatory Watershed Development. During 2008-09, 18 watershed projects with grant assistance of Rs.216 million were sanctioned and Rs.36.1million disbursed.

7. Capacity Building for Adoption of Technology: The NABARD introduced the scheme of Capacity Building for Adoption of Technology through training to farmers to facilitate them to adopt innovative methods of farming. The NABARD collaboration with different research institutes, Agricultural Science Centers, Agriculture Universities on bio-globules, vermin culture, bio-manures, organic farming, poly-house technology, medicinal and aromatic plant cultivation, etc.

8. Farmers Clubs: The Basic objectives of farmers Club program is to organize farmers in an informal organization to have easy & uninterrupted access to institutional credit and generate adequate bargaining power to deal with agencies, more importantly agriculture input suppliers and bulk produce buyers. Forum of Farmers' Club envisages farmers' exposure to agricultural technologies and practices, which are most appropriate to their agro-climate & motivate them to adopt them to enhance productivity, output & profitability.

9. Agricultural Insurance: Agriculture Insurance Company of India Ltd was established in December 2002 with an authorized capital of Rs.15,000 million. NABARD has subscribed the paid up capital of Rs.2,000 million and the remaining by five public sector general insurance companies

10. National Level Commodity Exchanges: Commodity market offers a market-based instrument to the farming community for managing risks and uncertainty in a liberalized environment. To strengthen the marketing infrastructure in the country, NABARD has been an equity partner in the major national level commodity exchanges, viz., Multi-Commodity Exchange and National Commodities and Derivatives Exchange.

11. Co-Financing: Commercial banks in particular are wary of taking credit risk while financing high tech, large scale, export oriented agricultural projects or those involving sunrise technologies, though they have expertise of financing industrial units having these characteristics. To instill confidence in banks and ensure credit flow to such projects, NABARD has entered into agreements for co-financing with 14 commercial banks.

12. Support to Weaker Sections: NABARD has introduced special programs for the uplifting weaker sections in the

society like the small and marginal farmers, scheduled castes and scheduled tribes, etc

13. Support to Small Farmers: Refinance policy of NABARD for production credit (short term loan) stipulates that banks earmark 30% of their total lending to small and marginal farmers

14. Support to Tribal Development: NABARD provides a separate line of credit on liberal terms, for Development of Tribal Population in predominantly tribal areas. NABARD also sanctions Short Term credit limits to cooperative banks for financing collection and marketing of various types of minor forest produce by scheduled tribes.

15. Supporting Grant to Agencies: NABARD continued to extend grant support to NGOs, RRBs, DCCBs, Farmer Clubs and Individual Rural Volunteers for promoting and nurturing quality SHGs. Efforts continued towards roping in new Self-Help Promoting Institutions and supporting the existing ones.

16. Capacity Building: Capacity building of stakeholders is crucial for up-scaling the SHG movement and maintaining the quality & sustainability of SHGs. NABARD supports capacity building programs for SHG members, officers of commercial banks, cooperative banks, RRBs, PRIs, and Government departments including IAS officers. With a view to fine tuning the strategies for up-scaling support to the MF sector, NABARD conducted three zonal workshops covering its own staff at Hyderabad, Lucknow and Patna.

17. Farmers' Technology Transfer Fund: NABARD has established Farmers' Technology Transfer Fund the objective is promoting & transferring technology, information dissemination, establishing linkages with market, enhancing productivity and production in agriculture, animal husbandry & fisheries through area based projects, conducting workshops, seminars and capacity building programs by

organizing farmers informal association, producer groups, joint liability groups.

18. Farm Innovation & Promotion

Fund: NABARD established the Farm Innovation and Promotion Fund to promoting innovative concepts and feasible projects in agriculture and allied activities, development of marketable prototypes, technology, patenting, extension support, marketing etc. Projects involving commodity exchange, rainfed rabi cropping, ultra high density orchard of guava, village farm development, protected vegetable cultivation in villages and efficient use of carbon & plant nutrients under dry land agriculture etc.

19. Research & Development Fund:

NABARD has constituted a Research and Development Fund for supporting activities, such as research projects, studies, training, conduct of seminars and other related activities on matters of importance to agriculture, agricultural operations and rural development. R&D Fund as grant assistance for research projects, studies, training and other activities like conduct of seminars, preparation of occasional papers etc. For increased dissemination of research findings in the areas of agriculture and rural development, publication of Occasional Papers is also supported by NABARD.

20. Institutional Development: The financial health and growth of Cooperative Banks & RRBs continue to be the area of concern to NABARD. In view of their role in credit dispensation and the changing economic environment, NABARD has been striving towards improving these institutions.

Findings:

1. NABARD is playing important Role in Agricultural development in India.
2. Farmers are not aware about NABARD Bank and Scheme of NABARD.

Conclusion:

The NABARD play very important role in rural and agricultural development. The institute is an apex body in agricultural sector hence they introduced new scheme related to agricultural. Currently NABARD bank is very actively work in India but lack of awareness about this institute the NABARD bank, State Government and Central Government can conduct awareness programs in villages, city and district level agricultural sector. The Scheme introduced the NABARD but the process of that scheme is very dely. The NABARD cannot provide One window system in taking loan and other facilities related scheme.

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